

The Impact of Training and Development on Staff Performance in Tertiary Educational Institutions in Sierra Leone.

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ABSTRACT

The strength of every institution is determined by the knowledge that resides in its staff and a well-trained and developed workforce is a recipe for outstanding performance and goal achievement. Nonetheless, the cost of training staffs in tertiary educational institutions is a critical sensation that restrains the conduct of training and developing them. This study seeks to carefully examine the impact of training and development on staff performance in tertiary educational institutions in Sierra Leone. The thrust for this theoretical research led to the retrieval of secondary sources published about the subject matter in order to structurally organize its content towards meaningful outcome. Analysis drawn from the retrieved information disclose to us that training can be conducted either on-the-job or off-the-job, which requires an assessment of the necessity of training which states the analysis of the organisation, person and task before an appropriate method could be selected. The reviewed content states that method selected should be followed by an evaluation process to ascertain its effect whether negative or positive. In relation to the evaluated evidences in the reviewed content, we are able to establish that training and development has a positive impact on employee performance as efficiency and effectiveness is activated or inspired by the quantum of knowledge that resides in employees. This study is relevant to human resource management practitioners, professors in tertiary educational institutions, management consultants and employees who are determined to improve their performance through training and development.

Key Words: Training and Development, Staff Performance, Tertiary Educational Institutions, Sierra Leone

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, the purpose of training and development has been to ensure that employees can effectively accomplish their jobs. Today, the business environment has changed, with intense pressure on organizations to stay ahead of the competition through innovation and reinvention (SHRM (2008)). Companies are experiencing great change due to new technologies, rapid development of knowledge, globalization of business, and development of e-commerce. Also, companies have to take steps to attract, retain, and motivate their work forces. Training is not a luxury; it is a necessity if companies are to participate in the global and electronic marketplaces by offering high-quality products and services. Training prepares employees to use new technologies, function in new work systems such as virtual teams, and communicate and cooperate with peers or customers who may be from different cultural backgrounds (Noe 2010). At one time, most people entered the workforce expecting a job for life, and for the majority that is what they experienced. Very often, members of the same family went to work for the same organization in the same town or city and stayed there until retirement. Some worked their way up from the shop floor to become 'management' while others were content to remain in a safe and stable environment with a regular pay packet. Others sought the 'office job' which they believed

gave them status and security for their working lives. That has all changed. Since the 1970s, there has been a decline in traditional industries and a subsequent loss of many routine and unskilled jobs. The workplace has become highly competitive and will become increasingly so. There is now a global economy to contend with. Gaining or maintaining an edge over competitors has become the priority of organizations, and also for individuals wishing to pursue a fulfilling career (Buckley et al 2009).

Conventionally, training and development was not viewed as an activity that could help companies create "value" and successfully deal with competitive challenges. Today, that view has changed. Companies that use innovative training and development practices are likely to report better financial performance than their competitors that do not. Training and development also helps a company to meet competitive challenges. Current recessionary economic times have resulted in cuts in training and development budgets. However, companies need to continue to rely on efficient and effective training practices to help employees strengthen or increase their skills in order to improve or make new products, generate new and innovative ideas, and provide high quality customer service. Also, development activities and career management are needed to prepare employees for managerial and leadership positions and to attract, motivate, and retain

talented employees at all levels and in all jobs. Training, development, and career management are no longer in the category of “nice to do”—they are a “must do” in order for companies to gain a competitive advantage and meet employees expectations. The role of training has broadened beyond training program design. Effective instructional design remains important, but training managers, human resource experts, and trainers are increasingly being asked to create systems to motivate employees to learn, create knowledge, and share that knowledge with other employees in the company. Training has moved from an emphasis on a one-time event to the creation of conditions for learning that can occur through collaboration, online learning, traditional classroom training, or a combination of methods. There is increased recognition that learning occurs outside the boundaries of a formal training course (Noe 2010). Tertiary educational institutions desire outstanding performance through its staff and such result can be activated by the knowledge that resides in the workforce; since knowledge should be continuously developed in order to achieve institutions’ objectives. Management of performance in these institutions has to do with the effective implementation of training and development programmes that are enlisted in the institutions’ strategic plans.

1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

During the nineteenth century Sierra Leone was a pioneer of western style education in Sub-Saharan Africa. Fourah Bay College, the first tertiary educational institution in the region, was founded in 1827, and the first boys’ school, Sierra Leone Grammar School, and the first girls’ school, Annie Walsh Memorial School, in the region founded in 1845 and 1849 respectively. The country was an important centre in training teachers, doctors and administrators for whole of West Africa in the first half of the nineteenth century. The education system that developed in Sierra Leone during the nineteenth and twentieth century was styled on the British education system. It was elitist in nature aimed at urban middle class and focused on the academically gifted who would go onto tertiary education before taking up positions as civil servants in the government. The country played an important role in the training of the first corps of administrators, doctors, and teachers in English-speaking West Africa in the first half of the last

century. At independence in 1961, Sierra Leone inherited a British-type education system, aimed largely at the urban middle class. The system was biased toward academically gifted students who entered tertiary education and found formal employment in government offices. In essence, the system was aimed at nurturing civil servants and government administrators. Most Sierra Leoneans were unable to access formal education or forced by circumstances to work before completing school. The Sierra Leone education system became an elitist system that excluded the majority of the population. Given this exclusive nature of the colonial education system, it is not surprising that literacy levels remained low. Staff development possibilities exist through scholarships from Commonwealth and other countries and through distance education. University lecturers also have study leave, which they use to upgrade their knowledge and/or to conduct research. To minimize the number of who go to study in other countries (and subsequently never return), scholarships for study in other African countries are now emphasized (World Bank 2007). The thrust for learning and educational development led to the establishment of other public and private universities; Njala University situated in the southern region of Sierra Leone and University of Makeni, the first private university founded by the Catholic Church situated in the northern region of Sierra Leone. Followed the establishment of the aforementioned institutions, are the influx of private professional colleges conducting tutorials, coupled with correspondence and online courses. The existence of government universities together with teachers training colleges, polytechnics and vocational institutes all geared towards developing the workforce in Sierra Leone, have made tremendous impact in the educational sector in the country. The effective and efficient functioning of these tertiary institutions requires highly trained and qualified staff in order to unleash their human capital so as to improve the educational system in the country. Training and staff capacity development is a recipe for outstanding performance. Nevertheless, the challenges surrounding the facets of training in these institutions are that, some government scholarships are not awarded to staff on merits but based on political affiliations particularly off-the-job training programmes. Unlike on-the-job training, the conduct of training covers the entire

workforce. Training and development programmes are very expensive particularly for staffs in tertiary institutions, considering the inventions of new technological equipment mainly in the sciences which as a result of the costs, cannot be afforded and also the process of sending staff out of the country for training is restrained by the limited training costs factored in institutions budgets.

1.2 AIM

The purpose of this study is to assess the impact of training and development on staff performance in tertiary educational institutions in Sierra Leone.

1.3 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

This segment outlines subsets of the research aim as conduit in achieving a structured review process.

- Define training and development and describe on-the-job and off-the-job training and explicate the need and benefits of training.
- Discuss the role of organization analysis, person analysis, and task analysis in needs assessment. Identify different methods used in needs assessment and classify the advantages and disadvantages of each method.
- Describe learning theories and explain the different methods of training and how they are applied to enhance performance.
- Discuss the implementation and evaluation of training programs
- Explain techniques used in achieving objectives through outstanding performance with well trained and developed workforce.

1.4 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Building staff capacity has proven to be a technique for staff retention and trained and developed staffs are a pride of organizations success. This study is significant to public and private corporations as the effective performance of staff is determined by the capacity of knowledge that resides in them. The study is also relevant to tertiary educational institutions as it serves as guide and a motivator towards

developing staff capacity for outstanding performance. This research will aid practising managers and will also contribute to the development of management profession as knowledge is a key factor in enhancing performance and achieving institutions objectives.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviews materials from published information in order to divulge the components that constitute facts about staff capacity building and its determinants on outstanding performance towards achieving institutions' objectives.

2.1 Definition of Training

Training refers to a planned effort by a company to facilitate employees' learning of job related competencies. These competencies include knowledge, skills, or behaviors that are critical for successful job performance. The goal of training is for employees to master the knowledge, skill, and behaviors emphasized in training programs and to apply them to their day-to-day activities (Noe 2010). Noe (2010) emphasised that for a company to gain a competitive advantage, its training has to involve more than just basic skill development. That is, to use training to gain a competitive advantage, a company should view training broadly as a way to create intellectual capital.

2.2 Definition of Development

Development is concerned with ensuring that a person's ability and potential are grown and realized through the provision of learning experiences or through self-directed (self-managed) learning. It is an unfolding process that enables people to progress from a present state of understanding and capability to a future state in which higher-level skills, knowledge and competencies are required (Armstrong (2009).

2.3 Types of training

2.3.1 On-the-job Training

On-the-job training (OJT) involves conducting training at a trainee's regular work station (desk, machine, etc.). This is the most common form of training; most employees receive at least some training and coaching on the job. Virtually any type of one-on-one instruction between co-workers or between the employee and supervisor

can be classified as OJT. Some have argued that, in general, employees learn and retain more through informal learning on the job than they do through formal training programs. On-the-job training has been promoted as a means for organizations to deal with the shortage of applicants who possess the skills needed to perform many current jobs, and as a means for organizations to deal with accelerating market cycles (Werner et al 2012).

2.3.2 Training as a Staff Function

As the problems and needs of each enterprise differ, a training organization may vary from company to company. However, a staff training organization is usually attached with an industrial relations department in view of its close relationships with other industrial relations functions. The role of the staff specialist consists of assisting the line by conducting the actual analysis of the training needs. Obviously, the role of the line involves determining the training priorities, allocating resources for 'on-the-job' training and evaluating the results of training. Thus, although every line official has his own training programmes for subordinates in the department, the bulk of the literature on training relates to staff training function (Dwivedi 2007).

2.3.3 Off-the-job Training

According to Ejiogu (2000) off-the-job training would include lecture, vestibule training, role playing, case study, discussion and simulation. Armstrong (1995) listed group exercises, team building, distance learning, outdoor and workshops as part of off-the-job training. He further explains that off-the-job training may be provided by members of the training department, external education and training establishments, or training providers, training consultants or guest speakers. He encourages line managers to be closely involved to bring reality into the classroom, to ease the transfer of learning, and to make sure that those involved in off-the-job training are carefully selected, briefed and monitored so as to ensure that they make the right contribution.

2.3.4 Learning and Training

The encouragement of learning makes use of a process model that is concerned with facilitating

the learning activities of individuals and providing learning resources for them to use. Conversely, the provision of training involves the use of a content model, which means deciding in advance, the knowledge and skills that need to be enhanced by training, planning the programme, deciding on training methods and presenting the content in a logical sequence through various forms of instruction (Armstrong 2006). A distinction is made by Sloman (2003a) between learning that 'lies within the domain of the individual' and training that 'lies within the domain of the organization. Today, the approach is to focus on individual learning and ensure that it takes place when required – 'just-for-you' and 'just-in-time' learning.

2.3.5 Training Needs

Turning specifically to training, since the potentially considerable financial and psychological costs involved, a great deal of consideration has to be given to deciding whether to embark on some form of training to meet individual learning and development needs. It is important to appreciate the circumstances which indicate whether or not training is required and there is a need to be thoroughly familiar with the methods, approaches and forms of analysis that have to be used in order to reach the decision to implement training. The criticality of this process cannot be over emphasized bearing in mind the consequences that might arise for organizations which provide too little training or no training at all when a real need exists (Buckley et al 2009).

2.3.6 Benefits of Training

Buckley et al (2009) indicates that there are numerous potential benefits to be gained by individuals and organizations from well-planned and effectively conducted training programmes designed to meet those needs. Individual trainees can benefit in a number of ways. In relation to their current positions Buckley (2009) emphasises that, trainees may gain greater intrinsic or extrinsic job satisfaction. Intrinsic job satisfaction may come from performing a task well and from being able to exercise a new repertoire of skills. Extrinsic job satisfaction may be derived from extra earnings accrued through improved job performance and the enhancement of career and promotion prospects both within and outside the organization to which they belong. He reiterated

that benefits for the organization include improved employee work performance and productivity; shorter learning time which could lead to less costly training and employees being 'on line' more quickly; decrease in wastage; fewer accidents; less absenteeism; lower labour turnover and greater customer or client satisfaction.

2.4 Needs Assessment

Effective training practices involve the use of a training design process. The design process begins with a needs assessment. Subsequent steps in the process include ensuring that employees have the motivation and basic skills necessary to learn, creating a positive learning environment, making sure that trainees use learned skills on the job, choosing the training method, and evaluating whether training has achieved the desired outcomes. Needs assessment refers to the process used to determine whether training is necessary. Needs assessment typically involves organizational analysis, person analysis, and task analysis (Noe 2010). Noe (2010) further describe the components of needs assessment and he elaborates that an organizational analysis considers the context in which training will occur. That is, organizational analysis involves determining the appropriateness of training, given the company's business strategy, its resources available for training, and support by managers and peers for training activities. He describes Person analysis that it helps to identify who needs training. Person analysis involves determining whether performance deficiencies result from a lack of knowledge, skill, or ability (a training issue) or from a motivational or work-design problem, identifying who needs training, and determining employees' readiness for training. He designate that Task analysis identifies the important tasks and knowledge, skills, and behaviors that need to be emphasized in training for employees to complete their tasks.

2.5 The Learning Organisation

The philosophy underpinning the learning organization concept, as expressed by Garvin (1993), is that learning is an essential ingredient if organizations are to survive; that learning at operational, policy and strategic levels needs to be conscious, continuous and integrated; and that management is responsible for creating an

emotional climate in which all staff can learn continuously.

2.6 Learning Theories

2.6.1 Reinforcement Theory

Reinforcement theory is based on the work of Skinner (1974). It expresses the belief that changes in behaviour take place as a result of an individual's response to events or stimuli, and the ensuing consequences (rewards or punishments). Individuals can be 'conditioned' to repeat the behaviour by positive reinforcement in the form of feedback and knowledge of results.

2.6.2 Cognitive Learning Theory

Cognitive learning involves gaining knowledge and understanding by absorbing information in the form of principles, concepts and facts, and then internalizing it. Learners can be regarded as powerful information processing machines (Armstrong 2006).

2.6.3 Experimental Learning Theory

People are active agents of their own learning (Reynolds et al 2002). Experiential learning takes place when people learn from their experience by reflecting on it so that it can be understood and applied. Learning is therefore a personal 'construction' of meaning through experience. 'Constructivists' such as Rogers (1983) believe that experiential learning will be enhanced through facilitation – creating an environment in which people can be stimulated to think and act in ways that help them to make good use of their experience.

2.6.4 Social Learning Theory

Social learning theory states that effective learning requires social interaction. Wenger (1998) suggested that we all participate in 'communities of practice' (groups of people with shared expertise who work together) and that these are our primary sources of learning. Bandura (1977) views learning as a series of information processing steps set in train by social interactions.

2.6.5 Motivation to Learn

Individuals must be motivated to learn. They should be aware that their present level of knowledge, skill or competence, or their existing attitude or behaviour, need to be developed or improved if they are to perform their work to their own and to others' satisfaction. They must,

therefore, have a clear picture of the behaviour they should adopt. To be motivated, learners must gain satisfaction from learning. They are most capable of learning if it satisfies one or more of their needs. Conversely, the best learning programmes can fail if they are not seen as useful by those undertaking them (Armstrong 2006).

2.6.6 Learning Culture

A learning culture is one that promotes learning because it is recognized by top management, line managers and employees generally as an essential organizational process to which they are committed and in which they engage continuously. Reynolds (2004) describes a learning culture as a 'growth medium', which will 'encourage employees to commit to a range of positive discretionary behaviours, including learning' and which has the following characteristics: empowerment not supervision, self-managed learning not instruction, long-term capacity building not short-term fixes. He suggests that to create a learning culture it is necessary to develop organizational practices that raise commitment amongst employees and 'give employees a sense of purpose in the workplace, grant employees opportunities to act upon their commitment, and offer practical support to learning.

2.7 Methods of Training

2.7.1 Coaching: Coaching is the process of developing the ability and experience of trainees by giving them systematically planned and progressively more 'stretching' tasks to perform coupled with continuous appraisal and counselling. This suggests the individual has acquired certain basic competencies or skills and that coaching is a method by which further improvement can be made through discussion and guided activity (Buckley et al 2009).

2.7.2 Mentoring: Mentoring is the process of using specially selected and trained individuals to provide guidance, pragmatic advice and continuing support, which will help the person or persons allocated to them to learn and develop. It has been defined by Clutterbuck (2004) as: 'Off-line help from one person to another in making significant transitions in knowledge, work or thinking. Hirsh and Carter (2002) suggest that mentors prepare individuals to perform better in the future and groom them for higher and greater things, i.e. career advancement. Armstrong (2006)

define mentoring as a method of helping people to learn, as distinct from coaching, which is a relatively directive means of increasing people's competence. It involves learning on the job, which must always be the best way of acquiring the particular skills and knowledge the job holder needs. He emphasised that mentoring also complements formal training by providing those who benefit from it with individual guidance from experienced managers who are 'wise in the ways of the organization.

2.7.3 E-learning: E-learning was defined by Pollard and Hillage (2001) as 'the delivery and administration of learning opportunities and support via computer, networked and web-based technology to help individual performance and development. He underscored that E-learning enhances learning by extending and supplementing face-to-face learning rather than replacing it. It enables learning to take place when it is most needed (just in time as distinct from just in case) and when it is most convenient. Learning can be provided in short segments or bites that focus on specific learning objectives.

2.7.4 Blended Learning: Blended learning is the use of a combination of learning methods to increase the overall effectiveness of the learning process by providing for different parts of the learning mix to complement and support one another. A blended learning programme might be planned for an individual using a mix of self-directed learning activities defined in a personal development plan, e-learning facilities, group action learning activities, coaching or mentoring, and instruction provided in an in-company course or externally. Generic training for groups of people might include e-learning, planned instruction programmes, planned experience and selected external courses. Within a training course a complementary mix of different training activities might take place, for example a skills development course for managers or team leaders might include some instruction on basic principles but much more time would be spent on case studies, simulations, role playing and other exercises (Armstrong 2009).

2.7.5 Self-directed Learning: Self-directed or self-managed learning involves encouraging individuals to take responsibility for their own learning needs, either to improve performance in

their present job or to develop their potential and satisfy their career aspirations. It can also be described as self-reflective learning, which is the kind of learning that involves encouraging individuals to develop new patterns of understanding, thinking and behaving (Mezirow 1985).

2.7.6 just-in-time Training: Just-in-time training is training that is closely linked to the pressing and relevant needs of people by its association with immediate or imminent work activities. It is delivered as close as possible to the time when the activity is taking place. The training will be based on an identification of the latest requirements, priorities and plans of the participants, who will be briefed on the live situations in which their learning has to be applied. The training programme will take account of any transfer issues and aim to ensure that what is taught is seen to be applicable in the current work situation (Armstrong 2009).

2.7.7 Bite-sized Training: Bite-sized training involves the provision of opportunities to acquire a specific skill or a particular piece of knowledge in a short training session that is focused on one activity such as using a particular piece of software, giving feedback, or handling an enquiry about a product or service of the company. It is often carried out through e-learning. It can be a useful means of developing a skill or understanding through a concentrated session or learning activity without diversions and is readily put to use in the workplace. But it can be weak in expanding individuals' intellectual capacity and holistic (or 'whole view') understanding of the business – essential qualities to enable employees to respond creatively to the challenges of today's knowledge economy. It can also be facile and too restricted and relies on the support of line managers, which is not always forthcoming. It is best for training employees in straightforward techniques that they can use immediately in their work or to complement, not replace, longer courses or developmental processes (Armstrong 2009).

2.7.8 Human Relations Training

Human relations training embraces broad areas including leadership, small group processes, communications, formal and informal organizations, morale and motivation, and building work teams. This method purports to

develop among participants an understanding among themselves so that they take into account the needs and aspirations of others. It stresses on attitudes and emotions, and develops leadership styles conducive to high morale and motivation. The human relations training is largely used with supervisors (Dwivedi 2007).

2.7.9 Preparing Training Materials

After training methods have been selected, the next logical step is to prepare or purchase training materials, depending upon whether the program is purchased or designed by the organization. If a training program is purchased from an outside vendor, training materials such as books, hand-outs, and videos will usually be part of the package. Programs designed in-house will require the preparation of materials. If the program is similar to past training programs, those materials may simply need to be modified to fit the current program (Werner et al 2012).

2.8 Levels of Learning

Different levels of learning exist and these need different methods and take different times. At the simplest level, learning requires direct physical responses, memorization and basic conditioning. At a higher level, learning involves adapting existing knowledge or skill to a new task or environment. At the next level, learning becomes a complex process when principles are identified in a range of practices or actions, when a series of isolated tasks have to be integrated, or when the process is about developing interpersonal skills. The most complex form of learning takes place when learning is concerned with the values and attitudes of people and groups. This is not only the most complex area, but also the most difficult (Armstrong 2006).

2.9 Evaluation of Training

Evaluation of training programmes provides assessment of various methods and techniques, sells training to management, identifies the weaknesses of training programmes and helps to accomplish the closest possible correlation between the training and the job. However, notwithstanding numerous programmes of training, very little effort has been made to assess them. Evaluation plan should be prepared at the very outset of the training programme and proper records should be maintained for this purpose (Dwivedi 2007).

2.10 Techniques for Evaluating the Effectiveness of Training

According to Yoder et al. (1958), there are several techniques for assessing the effectiveness of training programmes. These programmes can be evaluated by discontinuing them, using checklists, employing attitude and rating scales, using cost accounting, administering tests and plotting learning curves.

- Training programmes can be evaluated by observing its impact when they are discontinued. In cases where training programmes are ineffective, the improvement in performance disappears as soon as the training is discontinued.
- Checklists also provide an effective measure for evaluating training programmes. They have been largely used to assess the performance of a conference leader as well as to assess the extent of participation of conference members.
- Attitude and rating scales can be used to assess the efficacy of training. The participants may be asked to indicate the drawbacks of training in such a case. The cost accounting technique can be used to assess the effectiveness of training programmes. Substantial savings emerging from the programme indicate their effectiveness.
- Psychological tests can also be used to predict trainability for various jobs. Careful use of these tests can be of immense help in selecting individuals who can benefit from training, thereby minimizing the proportion of training failures. Tests can be used before and after training to assess their effectiveness.
- Learning curves have been found very useful in assessing the effectiveness of training. A learning curve can be plotted for each trainee. The quick learners may be sent into production while the slow ones may be replaced or transferred.

2.11 Transferring Training

It has been argued (Reynolds, 2004) that: 'The transfer of expertise by outside experts is risky since their design is often removed from the context in which work is created.' This is a fundamental problem and applies equally to internally run training courses where what has been taught can be difficult for people to apply in

the entirely different circumstances in their workplace. Training can seem to be remote from reality and the skills and knowledge acquired can appear to be irrelevant. This particularly applies to management or supervisory training but even the manual skills learnt in a training centre may be difficult to transfer.

2.12 Performance Management

One of the most important, if not the most important, of the responsibilities undertaken by managers is to ensure that the members of their team achieve high levels of performance. They have to know how to agree expectations and review results against those expectations, and how to decide what needs to be done to develop knowledge and skills, and where necessary performance. The organization may well have a performance management system which provides guidance on how this should be done, but ultimately it is up to managers. They are the people on the spot. Performance management systems only work if managers want them to work and are capable of making them work. They have to believe that their time is well spent in the process of managing performance. They need the skills required to set objectives, conduct formal performance reviews and provide feedback (Armstrong 2010).

2.12.1 Definition of Performance Management

Performance management (PM) is the process of managing the execution of an organization's strategy. It is how plans are translated into results. Think of PM as an umbrella concept that integrates familiar business improvement methodologies with technology. In short, the methodologies no longer need to be applied in isolation—they can be orchestrated. PM is sometimes confused with human resources and personnel systems, but it is much more encompassing. PM comprises the methodologies, metrics, processes, software tools, and systems that manage the performance of an organization. PM is overarching, from the C-level executives cascading down through the organization and its processes. To sum up its benefit, it enhances broad cross-functional involvement in decision making and calculated risk taking by providing tremendously greater visibility with accurate, reliable, and relevant information—all aimed at executing an organization's strategy (Coking 2004).

2.12.2 Appraisal and Performance Management

There is considerable pressure on organizations to adopt performance control approaches to appraisal, and that even in organizations that espouse an HRM orientation, beliefs that emphasize rationality and efficiency may become part of a set of taken-for-granted assumptions. Clearly an organization which desires to develop appraisal with a development focus will need to challenge such assumptions but also accommodate them. The result is likely to be the emergence of sophisticated models that make use of multiple techniques that satisfy the demands of multiple users (Bratton et al 1999).

2.12.3 Measuring Performance in Achieving Objectives

Measurement is an important concept in performance management. It is the basis for providing and generating feedback, it identifies where things are going well to provide the foundations for building further success, and it indicates where things are not going so well, so that corrective action can be taken. Measuring performance is relatively easy for those who are responsible for achieving quantified targets, for example sales. It is more difficult in the case of knowledge workers, for example scientists. But this difficulty is alleviated if a distinction is made between the two forms of results – outputs and outcomes. An output is a result that can be measured quantifiably, while an outcome is a visible effect that is the result of effort but cannot necessarily be measured in quantified terms (Armstrong 2009).

2.13 Achieving Objectives through Outstanding Performance with well Trained and Developed Workforce.

There has been a notion that well trained and developed staffs have the capability to enhance outstanding performance which will ultimately lead to the achievement of institutions' objectives. This notion is factual since performance can only be improved as a result of endowed tacit and explicit knowledge that resides in the workforce. Staff in tertiary educational institutions in Sierra Leone requires continual capacity building programmes to increase their performance since they are trainers or developers of the country's intellectual capital; a capital that in turn will be invested towards the development of the country and increase its level in the human development index. The challenges observed in the process of developing staff capacity in Sierra Leone are that, most times analysis of the organisation, person to

be identified for training and the elements of task analysis (knowledge, skills, and behaviours) that should be focused on before implementing training programmes are not considered sometimes important and that has led to training the wrong employees and consequently experience a negative feedback in the implementation of knowledge gained during the training. Another challenge is that, for those who are objectively selected also experience difficulties in the learning process, particularly those that travel out of the country or on off-the-job training programmes.

The retrieval of information from secondary sources has revealed a whole lot of facts about the significance of staff capacity building and the careful perusal of available content in the review column has espoused certainties that training and development programmes cannot be undertaken without an assessment of its needs and even though needs are assessed, careful selection of appropriate methods should be done in order for implementation of such training programme to be effective. Having thoroughly examined the reviewed content, we have been able to identify cost of training to be the ultimate fissure which we seek to address.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The conduct of this research stems from theoretical perspectives and that enabled us to obtain information from secondary sources in order to thoroughly examine the elements of training and development. Information is retrieved from published human resource management books, materials on training and development and other relevant facts published about the subject matter.

4.0 ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Training and development is realised as an accelerating dynamism towards outstanding performance and goal achievement. Facts have proven the veracities of training that it helps to improve staff performance and transform previously unsatisfactory behaviours that have been hindering their commitment towards work. On-the-job training which takes place within the working environment is seen to be a significant component since it involves coaching and mentoring which serves as a motivator towards staff commitment in training programmes. Off-the-job training is also another key instrument but

the selection of such training components first of all requires a training needs assessment which helps trainers or human resource management practitioners to be able to identify the necessity of conducting a training programme. The significance of conducting a training programme is that, it helps staff in tertiary institutions to learn new skills and competencies and develop their intrinsic and extrinsic behaviours.

The conduct of training needs assessment is centred on three major elements: organisational analysis, person analysis and task analysis. Organisational analysis describes the appropriateness of a training programme in relations to the business strategy and its resources available for training. Person analysis identifies the person to be trained and examine his previous performance deficiencies whether it was as a result of insufficient capacity of knowledge to execute task entrusted to him/her. It also examines the person's readiness or willingness to undergo further training in order to enhance capacity. Lastly, task analysis describes the knowledge, behaviour and task to be accentuated during a training programme.

We discussed three key learning theories in this study in order to fulfil the desires of readers to properly understand the subject matter. Reinforcement theory which is the first theory discussed, reinforces staff behaviour which generate feedback and knowledge of result. Cognitive learning theory states that knowledge can be gained through the absorption of information in the form of principles facts and relevant issues discussed in a training programme, and such facts can be processed by the learner which transforms to vital knowledge that aid staffs in the execution of their duties. Experimental learning theory discloses that staffs can learn through careful experimentation of activities in the workplace or through past experiences of other staff members and finally social learning theory emphasised the importance of social interactions with others in the work place, as the working environment is clustered with diverse disciplines and competences. The methods used in training and developing staff capacity should be carefully selected by the training director or a specialist in the human resource management department. After the conduct of needs assessment, whether on-the-job training which involves coaching and

mentoring or off-the-job training is applicable or suit the conduct of the training programme, care must be taken to identify and select the best or appropriate method so as to produce satisfactory result in the implementation of knowledge gained during the training programme.

The selection of the appropriate training method is followed by the implementation and evaluation process to ascertain whether the right method was selected and the impact it has on the training programme. Also the evaluation process unveils actualities about new learned skills, behaviours and competences. This process also discloses information about inappropriate training method selected and the implications of such unfruitful selection process. The aforementioned divulge that outstanding performance of staff in tertiary institutions in Sierra Leone is determined by the appropriate training method selected in order to develop their capacity. As is it a well-known concept, trained and developed workforce can perform more than staff whose development potentials are restrained by the limited cost in the training budget.

Managing performance in tertiary institutions is a key element which does not only focus on planning the task to be performed but also evaluate its outcome. The effects of staff capacity on performance is triggered by the institutions motivating instruments which, if not carefully addressed, can lead to staff restraining from unleashing their knowledge capital.

5.0 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The careful collection of vital information in order to develop this study have revealed evident facts about the impact of training and development on staff performance in tertiary educational institutions in Sierra Leone. Retrieved information have been able to make us understand that training can either be conducted on-the-job or off-the-job and cannot be implemented without a consideration of its needs and the conduct of a needs assessment which constitutes organisational analysis, person analysis and task analysis. Also, the theories used in this study (reinforcement, cognitive learning, experimental learning and social learning theories) revealed the process of the significance in training programme. The objective selection of appropriate methods for a training programme whether coaching, mentoring

or other, reveals the actualities that it helps institutions staff to learn and be able to understand the concepts taught or delivered in the training. Evaluation has also helps us to understand that training should not only be conducted but should also be evaluated to ascertain its impact whether positive or negative and consequently performance of staff should be effectively managed. Our critical analysis of the theories and facts derived substantiate that training and development has a positive impact on staff performance in tertiary educational institutions in the sense that the invention of new technological equipment's requires training and also the development of new strategies for competitive advantage requires training. Looking at training and development in a wide perspective, discloses that every institution in the world requires a well-trained and developed workforce if it is to function well and achieve its objectives. This research was conducted on theoretical perspectives that is why secondary information was collected. Nevertheless, further empirical research can be conducted in order to deal with specific elements of training and development.

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